

1 **Sex analysis in marine biological systems: insights and opportunities**

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10

11 **Abstract**

12 The ocean is facing unprecedented challenges with the escalating impacts of climate change and other
13 pressures threatening ecosystems and the many benefits they provide. Effective strategies for reversing
14 the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services rely on knowledge of how marine organisms,
15 populations, and communities respond to environmental change. A fundamental, but often
16 overlooked biological characteristic of organisms is biological sex – which is distinct from
17 sociocultural gender. Here, we address: a) how sex influences the physiology, behavior and ecology
18 of marine organisms, populations, and communities; b) how this knowledge is generated in current
19 marine biology research; and c) how sex analysis may be more broadly applied in future research.
20 Through review of sex analysis applications in marine biological research we find that sex broadly
21 affects the morphology, physiology, behavior, and distribution of organisms and population across
22 taxa, with evidence of sex-specific differences in survival to thermal stress, timing of biological
23 mechanisms, and energetics. Sex analysis reveals pervasive effects of sex on a suite of biological
24 processes and scales of biological organizations. We found that sex analysis is most commonly

25 applied to studies of organisms' life history traits and population dynamics, but possible effects on
26 communities are rarely addressed. Existing evidence of sex-based differences across taxa and
27 biological levels of organization highlights that including sex as a biological variable in research is
28 essential to understanding marine systems and their responses to environmental change. To facilitate
29 future integration of sex into marine biological research, we synthesize current approaches, propose
30 solutions to methodological and logistical challenges, and lay out guidelines for future research.

31

32 **In a nutshell:**

- 33 • Sex analysis incorporates biological sex in each step of the research process, from strategic
34 considerations for establishing research priorities to formulating questions, designing
35 methodologies, and interpreting results.
- 36 • In numerous scientific areas, such as biomedicine and artificial intelligence, integrating sex
37 into research design and analysis has produced new insights and solutions, but a clear
38 understanding of sex analysis for marine biological systems is not available.
- 39 • We reviewed how sex-based differences are studied in marine biological research. We found
40 that sex analysis is most commonly applied to the study of organisms and populations, but not
41 communities of marine organisms. Sex influences physiological, morphological and
42 behavioral mechanisms in 90.4% of the studies.
- 43 • We provide guidelines for incorporating sex analysis into future research and highlighting
44 examples of methodological approaches in data collection, laboratory and field experiments,
45 mathematical modelling, and meta-analysis.

46 (MAIN TEXT STARTS HERE)

47 Effective ocean management and mitigation of climate change impacts depend on understanding
48 organism and ecosystem responses to anthropogenic and environmental change (Frazão Santos *et al.*

49 2020). Increasing this understanding and capacity to produce useful and usable knowledge is a major
50 focus for the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable development (2021-2030) and
51 the Sustainable Development Goals (particularly Goal 14, Life Below Water) (Singh *et al.* 2021) and
52 will require innovative frameworks and technologies. We argue that sex analysis (Panel 1) provides
53 opportunities for innovation and for advancing our understanding of how marine biological systems
54 respond to environmental change.

55 Sex refers to biological attributes of living organisms. Importantly, it is distinguished from gender,
56 which refers to psychological, social and cultural factors that shape attitudes, behaviors, stereotypes,
57 technologies and knowledge in human societies (Tannenbaum *et al.* 2019). Sex describes differences
58 in sexual characteristics within living organisms that go beyond their reproductive functions and
59 affect appearance, physiology or neuroendocrine, behavioral, and metabolic systems (Tannenbaum
60 *et al.* 2019). In marine organisms, sex takes many forms (e.g., male, female, simultaneous or
61 sequential hermaphrodite) influenced by genetic and molecular mechanisms (e.g., sexual or asexual
62 reproduction) and environmental factors (e.g., ambient temperature). Reviews have found that sex is
63 often overlooked in laboratory experiments investigating the response of a variety of marine
64 organisms to ocean acidification (Ellis *et al.* 2017) and temperature increase (Pottier *et al.* 2021). In
65 the broader field of biological sciences, recent studies have addressed the role of sex in research on
66 mammals (Woitowich *et al.* 2020; Garcia-Sifuentes and Maney 2021), and specifically on mice as
67 model organisms in experimental studies (Zajitschek *et al.* 2020). But the extent to which sex-based
68 differences are explicitly addressed across taxa, species, populations, and communities in marine
69 biology research has not been examined. Discipline-specific guidelines are needed to support
70 researchers in considering sex when formulating hypotheses and methods in their own fields
71 (Tannenbaum *et al.* 2019; European Commission 2020). To date, such guidelines do not exist in
72 marine biology, and for biology doing research in natural environments in general.

73 These potential knowledge gaps have direct implications for environmental management, including
74 ocean management. Fisheries management, for example, may fail to achieve sustainability if sex-
75 based differences in stock assessments are ignored (Williams *et al.* 2012; Easter *et al.* 2020). Fisheries
76 that catch large individuals (Easter *et al.* 2020) may de facto target females in species where females
77 mature larger than males (Pauly 2019). Disproportionally high mortality among large fecund females
78 can significantly decrease stock productivity (Hixon *et al.* 2014). Thus, ignoring sex could have
79 unintended negative consequences for marine populations and ocean management outcomes.

80 Here, we review studies that address sex-based differences in marine biology research to exemplify
81 a larger need for considering sex in biological research across marine and terrestrial systems. We
82 focus on marine systems because of the urgency of the challenges and remaining large gaps in
83 knowledge of oceans. Our aims are: (1) to understand the role of sex in influencing morphological,
84 physiological, behavioral, and ecological processes across marine taxa and at different levels of
85 biological organization—organism, population, species, and community levels; (2) to understand the
86 methodological approaches and experimental techniques researchers use to address sex-based
87 differences. We conducted a critical review of research design and methods from studies applying
88 sex analysis (materials and methods in Supporting information, WebTables 1-3, WebFigure 1). We
89 also identified best practices for sex analysis. From this review, we propose a set of guidelines for
90 integrating sex analysis into field research, laboratory and field experiments, mathematical modelling,
91 and meta-analyses. Finally, we discuss the challenges and opportunities for applying sex analysis in
92 future biology research, including the methodological and logistic challenges of considering sex.

93

94 **Results**

95 **Sex-based differences across taxa and levels of biological organization**

96 All the studies in our pool integrated sex into the research design and examined sex-specific
97 differences in biological processes, predominantly at the organismal and population levels (Fig. 1,
98 detailed examples in WebTable 4). Sex-based differences were found in individual appearance,
99 morphology, and physiology, as well as differences in individual sex-based age and growth within or
100 between populations (Fairbairn 2016). Sex influences individual and populations behaviors, including
101 foraging and predator avoidance (Cherry *et al.* 2020). Sex-specific individual and population
102 behaviors are driven by sex-based morphology (Montoya *et al.* 2019), or different energy
103 requirements associated with reproductive investment of males and females (Elliott Smith *et al.*
104 2015). Sex-based differences also influence courtship, competition, communication, and care of
105 offspring (Cherry *et al.* 2020). At the species level, sex can influence spatial segregation of species
106 across space and time. Females and males spatially segregate likely because of temperature or salinity
107 ranges preferences (Péron *et al.* 2015) or because of sex-specific habitat preferences driven by
108 differences in energetic requirements (Acevedo *et al.* 2014). None of the studies addressed the role
109 of sex at the community level, for instance, in food webs or in interspecific interactions.

110 A majority of studies (90.4%, N=384 in total) detected sex-based differences in biological processes
111 (Fig. 1). The fraction of studies detecting sex-specific differences varies from a minimum of 78.9%
112 in studies of distribution and sexual segregation of species (N=18), to a maximum of 95.2% of studies
113 of sex-specific differences in genetic mechanisms at the organismal level (N=62). When studies are
114 grouped by taxa, we found sex-based differences detected in 89.7% of studies on average, with the
115 percentages varying from 87.1% of studies of elasmobranchs (N=31), to 95.1% of studies of
116 crustaceans (N=41) (Fig. 2, WebTable 5).

117 Sex-based differences have been studied more frequently in some taxa (Fig. 2). With respect to
118 movement ecology, for instance, we found that spatial and temporal sexual segregation has been
119 studied especially in chordates, such as teleost fish species (eg Borg *et al.* 2014), seabirds (eg Paiva
120 *et al.* 2017), and marine mammals (eg Briscoe *et al.* 2018). In contrast, the role of sex-specific

121 differences in physiological processes were investigated in fish (eg Murray and Baumann 2020) and
122 invertebrates (eg Rocha *et al.* 2019) more than in mammals, birds and reptiles (WebTable 4).

123

124 **Methodological approaches to sex analysis**

125 We provide an overview of research design approaches and methods from studies applying sex
126 analysis below, with additional detailed examples of their practical application in WebTable 6. In
127 Table 1 we synthesized the same research design approaches and methods in the form of guidelines.

128 **Data collection in field research (Fig 4a).** Studies addressing sex-based differences collected data
129 about the sex of marine organisms through a suite of strategies and techniques. With data
130 disaggregated and reported by sex, researchers were then able to consider sex as a covariate in the
131 subsequent research phases. Techniques to detect the sex of targeted organisms span from
132 morphometric measurements of specific body organs (Mutalipassi *et al.* 2018) to the analysis of
133 genetic markers for molecular sex identification (Brown *et al.* 2016; Rees *et al.* 2017). Combining
134 genetics and genomics has been fruitful in sexing many species, such as sea turtles (Banerjee *et al.*
135 2021) and crustaceans (Shi *et al.* 2018). To detect sex when tagging and tracking marine organisms,
136 studies have combined multiple data collection and sexing techniques, such as, for instance, flipper
137 tagging, satellite tracking and genetic markers (Rees *et al.* 2017).

138 Researchers have also addressed how sex may affect the process of data collection. Data collection
139 can result in skewed sex-ratios of surveyed organisms or of the collected data. Skewed sex-ratios in
140 data can depend on sex-specific biological mechanisms or sex-specific selectivity of data collection
141 techniques. For instance, in a study of white sharks (*Carcharodon carcharias*) off the coast of central
142 California, USA, Kanive *et al.* (2015) speculated that the higher numbers of observed older males
143 might depend on higher mortality among younger females or a smaller number of observed females
144 due to differences in behavior. By innovatively combining detections from acoustic tags and dorsal

145 fin photographic identifications, Chapple *et al.* (2016) found that sex-specific patterns in migration
146 of white sharks resulted in disparate capture probabilities between males and females, which affected
147 the observed sex ratio. These results suggest that the higher numbers of observed older males reported
148 by Kanive *et al.* (2015) likely depends on differences in behavior between males and females, and
149 not on higher mortality of females (Chapple *et al.* 2016). Future research will need to explore the
150 potential causes of the observed skewed sex ratios in field population.

151 Another approach to robustly including sex and sex analysis in field studies requires detecting
152 potential sex bias in existing datasets. Data collected through fishery-dependent surveys can be biased
153 towards females or males depending on species and fishery type. For instance, in the highly dimorphic
154 snow crab (*Chionoecetes opilio*) in the Eastern Bering Sea, females that are smaller than males have
155 no commercial value and are underrepresented in fishery-dependent survey data since fisheries only
156 target large males (Murphy *et al.* 2018). To fit sex-specific state-space models, Murphy *et al.* (2018)
157 used data collected by the annual US National Marine Fisheries Service bottom trawl summer survey
158 in combination with fishery survey data to obtain robust data for both males and females.

159 **Laboratory and field experiments (Fig. 4b).** Studies conducting experiments in controlled or
160 natural environments either included organisms of each sex, or sexed organisms included in the
161 experiment. Examples involved crustaceans (Yli-Renko *et al.* 2018) and fish species (Dessen *et al.*
162 2016).

163 Another approach to considering sex in experiments is to account for sex-specific differences of male,
164 female and hermaphroditic organisms in baseline conditions – before experiments are conducted.
165 Baseline studies of model species were conducted to statistically determine sex-based intraspecific
166 variation prior to the experiments, since variation between sexes may be greater than variation related
167 to the experimental treatment. In ecotoxicology, for instance, behavior has been increasingly studied
168 as a response variable that links the biochemical effects of contamination with the physiology of
169 individuals (Saaristo *et al.* 2018). In a laboratory study of baseline conditions for ecotoxicological

170 analysis, Cherry *et al.* (2020) found sex-based differences in the behavior of the intertidal amphipod
171 (*Echinogammarus marinus*) stimulated by altering periods of light and dark. Ignoring sex-based
172 differences in baseline conditions may result in erroneously considering behavioral differences as a
173 result of the biochemical effect of contamination (Cherry *et al.* 2020).

174 Studies have also considered the role played by sex when evaluating potential explanations for sex-
175 based differences in the response variables. For instance, Nørregaard *et al.* (2018) studied gill and
176 liver pathologies in sculpins (*Myoxocephalus spp.*) as health indicators of the possible effects of
177 mining activity at two sites in Greenland waters. Sex-specific differences in heavy metal
178 concentration were found in fourhorn sculpins but not in shorthorn sculpins. The authors questioned
179 if these results depend on the skewed females-males sample ratio, on differences in metabolism and
180 physiology between species, or on differences in environmental conditions between sites (Nørregaard
181 *et al.* 2018). Further investigation of factors causing sex-specific heavy metal concentration is needed
182 since confounding effects can lead to misinterpretation of ecotoxicological responses in these species
183 and, importantly, in the implications of results for pollution mitigation (Nørregaard *et al.* 2018;
184 Kaarsholm *et al.* 2018).

185 **Mathematical modelling (Fig 4c).** Studies developing mathematical models of biological processes
186 have accounted for sex-based differences by including sex as an explanatory variable. Models were
187 fitted aggregating or disaggregating data by sex and then modelling parameters were compared. This
188 allowed researchers to detect differences between sexes in the biological and/or environmental
189 predictors and to assess the role of sex and sex-based differences in the modelled processes. For
190 instance, Tsai *et al.* (2015) compared single- and two-sex demographic models of shortfin mako shark
191 (*Isurus oxyrinchus*) in the Northwest Pacific. They found that single-sex demographic models that
192 ignored sexual dimorphism and mating mechanisms underestimated the risk of population decline
193 (Tsai *et al.* 2015).

194 Another approach for taking into consideration sex-based differences is to check any statistically
195 significant differences in the data disaggregated by sex before fitting models. For instance, in the case
196 of finetooth sharks (*Carcharhinus isodon*) in the Western North Atlantic Ocean, by applying an
197 analysis of covariance (ANCOVA), significant differences were detected for length to mass
198 conversions, for which sex-specific growth models were fitted, but not for body length measurements,
199 for which one model was fitted with aggregated data (Vinyard *et al.* 2019).

200 To account for the role of sex and sex-specific differences when modelling population dynamics,
201 researchers have also upgraded existing modelling approaches, such as stock assessment models or
202 age-at-growth models, by including sex-based factors. For instance, to estimate the performance of
203 stock assessments of blue marlin (*Makaira nigricans*) in the Pacific Ocean, Su *et al.* (2011) applied
204 Monte Carlo simulations to an assessment method that accounts for seasonal movement and sexual
205 dimorphism. A population dynamics model that includes spatial structure, and sex and age structure
206 was constructed and fitted to fisheries data along with information on the relative density of the
207 population over space (Su *et al.* 2011). The authors found that the previous estimates of maximum
208 sustainable yield and the related spawning stock biomass were overestimated when the assessment
209 method ignored seasonal movement and sexual dimorphism (Su *et al.* 2011).

210 **Meta-analysis (Fig. 4d).** Studies have explored the potential role of sex as a biological variable when
211 defining meta-analysis research questions. Meta-analyses have identified potential research gaps in
212 specific research fields, biological or environmental mechanisms. For instance, Ellis *et al.* (2017)
213 analyzed the role of sex in experimental ocean acidification research. They found that only 3.9% of
214 studies statistically assessed sex-based differences in ocean acidification responses, but that, in the
215 majority of the studies where tested, sex significantly influenced marine organisms responses (Ellis
216 *et al.* 2017).

217 Meta-analyses were also applied to explore the variability of sex-specific differences across species
218 and biological mechanisms. A systematic review of sex-based differences in thermal acclimation

219 capacity across ectotherms, for example, found that females had greater heat tolerance plasticity than
220 males in some species and not in others (Pottier *et al.* 2021). Sensitivity analyses were also used to
221 explore variation of the synthetic findings (Lortie *et al.* 2015) by disaggregating studies including or
222 excluding sex-based differences, or female and male organisms (Ellis *et al.* 2017; Pottier *et al.* 2021).

223 When collecting studies for meta-analysis, researchers have considered how sex and sex-specific
224 differences were considered in the set of original studies. Since meta-analysis statistically synthesizes
225 results from separate studies (Vetter *et al.* 2013), results can be sex-biased if sex-specific differences
226 are not considered in the original studies. In a meta-analysis investigating sex-specific differences in
227 contaminant concentrations in fish, for instance, Madenjian *et al.* (2016) discarded studies reporting
228 sex-specific difference in contaminant concentrations based on determinations in just one body part
229 (e.g., muscle or liver tissue), because the spatial distribution of contaminants within fish bodies may
230 vary between the sexes. Consequently, a sex-specific difference in contaminant concentrations based
231 on determinations in just one part of the fish may not accurately capture the sex difference in whole-
232 fish contaminant concentrations (Madenjian *et al.* 2016).

233

234 **Discussion**

235 This review highlights that sex-based differences have been documented for a broad array of
236 biological processes in marine systems: over 90% of studies that explicitly consider sex found sex-
237 based differences. This result may overestimate the influence of sex, as, for example, researchers may
238 be more likely to apply sex analysis in systems where previous research has highlighted sex-specific
239 differences. Nevertheless, this high percentage supports the prediction that sex can potentially
240 influence the vast majority of biological processes—from development to physiology and behavior.
241 The sex-based differences we documented across levels of biological organization and taxa in this
242 review may depend on species characteristics or the methodological approaches used to include sex
243 in marine biology research. Our results may also be influenced by our approach of targeting only

244 studies about sex-based differences in biological processes, and excluding search terms such as
245 “gender”, which scientists sometimes use erroneously to refer to the sex of living organisms (Madsen
246 *et al.* 2017).

247 Nonetheless, our findings of the prevalence of sex-based differences across taxa and subfields
248 highlight the importance of considering if and how sex can influence research design, analysis, and
249 results (Tannenbaum *et al.* 2019). If sex does not play a role, this is valuable information that must
250 be reported, and sex may be omitted in subsequent research. If sex is difficult or impossible to
251 determine or control for, we suggest that challenges and limitations related to considering sex in the
252 study be reported. These challenges may be addressed through future advances in methodological
253 approaches or theory. Reporting sex will help improve transparency in study design and, ultimately,
254 the accuracy of findings (Woitowich *et al.* 2020) as required by funding agencies (White *et al.* 2021)
255 and peer-review life science journals (eg Editorial Board 2022).

256 The guidelines we report in Table 1 can provide a framework for researchers to approach sex analysis
257 in marine biological research design. More broadly, these guidelines can be relevant for research
258 design and hypothesis in other biological systems, such as terrestrial ones, that share similar
259 processes and challenges (Ruckstuhl and Clutton-Brock 2006; Pinsky *et al.* 2022). The focus of this
260 study on marine system was aimed at limiting the scope of the review effort, but results and general
261 insights likely apply to terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems as well. Specific aspects of sex-based
262 differences have been studied in both terrestrial and marine domains, for instance, to understand the
263 many different forms and possible causes of sexual segregation in vertebrates (Ruckstuhl and Clutton-
264 Brock 2006), of adult sex ratio in wild animal populations (Ancona *et al.* 2017), and of thermal
265 response in ectotherm species (Pottiers *et al.* 2021), but more study is needed.

266 Numerous challenges need to be addressed when collecting and reporting data by sex—and may
267 account for why sex is not always included in research design. Methodologically, a fundamental
268 requirement for analyzing sex in biological research is that data are disaggregated by sex. When

269 collecting data or observing species in their natural environment, it can be difficult to determine sex
270 in species for which sex differences are not apparent, have not been previously assessed (Fairbairn
271 2016) or vary with geographical and environmental factors (Nam *et al.* 2018). For many species,
272 histological and genetic analyses may be necessary (Medeiros *et al.* 2012). This, however, may be
273 costly, invasive, and time consuming. In many cases where sexing organisms in the field is
274 methodologically possible, sampling organisms of both sexes along their life cycle can be logistically
275 challenging (Griffiths *et al.* 2018), as in the case of wide-ranging species (Kanive *et al.* 2015).
276 Tradeoff between sample size and sampling costs can be critical (Ryan 2013).

277 Despite many difficulties, not considering sex may lead to erroneous results (Tannenbaum *et al.*
278 2019). Sex-based differences could be approached incrementally. Even a small sample sizes can lead
279 to insightful sex-based differences in living organisms, especially for species or biological processes
280 for which previous knowledge is not available (Sequeira *et al.* 2019). The sample size can then be
281 increased to answer new research questions and may lead to new knowledge about species' natural
282 history.

283 Technological advances may also offer solutions to these methodological and logistic challenges.
284 Miniaturization of tags, for example, has allowed studies of seabirds to expand from the sex-specific
285 studies of adults to also include juveniles (Fay *et al.* 2015). The use of drones to collect whale blow
286 'snot' has drastically reduced time and costs traditionally spent on vessels to manually collect whale
287 tissue samples with biopsy crossbows (Atkinson *et al.* 2021) while providing a better understanding
288 of whale individual sex, health, pregnancy status, genome and microbiome (Bennett *et al.* 2015;
289 Keller and Willke 2019).

290 This review found that marine community ecology is a subfield of marine biology research where
291 sex-based differences have been understudied likely because the logistical and methodological
292 challenges mentioned above are amplified when analyzing sex across multiple interacting species.
293 However, ignoring the role of sex in community ecology studies is particularly problematic given

294 that communities are likely to re-structure as a consequence of climate-induced changes at individual
295 and population levels (Rilov *et al.* 2019). And the response to climate stressors of organisms and
296 populations can be sex-specific (Ellis *et al.* 2017; Pottier *et al.* 2021). Although intraspecific
297 differences in biological processes has increased in interest among community ecologists (Start and
298 De Lisle 2018), community-level consequences of sex-specific differences remain poorly understood
299 (De Lisle *et al.* 2022). Community ecology models tend to assume ‘asexual’ adult organisms (Violle
300 *et al.* 2012) that do not capture, for instance, sex-specific behaviors or resource use of females, males
301 or hermaphrodites, and, consequently, sex-based differences in consumer-resource relationships of
302 species interactions (De Lisle *et al.* 2022). The effects of sex-based differences on the structure and
303 dynamics of ecological communities represents a vast field for future investigation.

304

305 **Conclusions**

306 Sex fundamentally influences a suite of biological mechanisms across taxa and levels of biological
307 organizations. Challenges, such as sexing marine organisms, particularly in offshore or deep ocean
308 habitats, has impeded sex analysis in marine biology. Overcoming these challenges and integrating
309 sex analysis more broadly into biological research holds potential for more effective solutions to
310 global change and biodiversity loss. To unlock this potential, cultural biases likely affecting theories
311 and research design, such as in reproductive biology (Orr *et al.* 2020), need to be questioned and
312 addressed by researches, funding institutions, and peer-review journals.

313 Based on this review and synthesis, we provide guidelines to facilitate future incorporation of sex in
314 research design and analysis. Understanding specifically how to integrate sex analysis across the
315 research process can increase the robustness of results and spark research innovation and technology
316 advances.

317 While researchers are called to consider sex and sex analysis in their research hypothesis and design,
318 funding agencies will need to incentivize fundamental research aimed at uncovering differences
319 between sexes, and how these may influence biological systems across multiple levels of biological
320 organization. This knowledge is needed to better inform global-scale analyses – that necessarily
321 reduce the complexity of ecosystems or models – accounting for natural history traits shaped through
322 evolution. Uncovering nuances in sex-specific species’ life history traits and behaviors, and how they
323 shape communities will help broadening our knowledge and inform effective conservation.

324

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330

331 **Author contribution**

332 EG designed the study with the contribution of LS and FM; EG performed the analysis and wrote the
333 first draft of the manuscript and the figures; all authors contributed to the final version of the article.

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- 483

Panel 1: Sex analysis

Sex analysis is the process of incorporating biological sex considerations into research design and analysis (European Commission 2020). In sex analysis, sex is integrated not only as a covariate into an experimental treatment, but as a factor that can influence (or confound) the research design, analysis, and interpretation of the results. The aim of sex analysis is to understand how sex should be considered in each step of the research process, from strategic considerations for establishing priorities to formulating questions, designing methodologies, and interpreting data (Schiebinger 2014). The ultimate goal of sex analysis is to increase research rigor, reproducibility, generalizability, and findings accuracy (Woitowich *et al.* 2020; White *et al.* 2021). Sex analysis can take many forms depending on the specific research field, topic, systems, or organisms. Sex analysis is not only applied to investigate sex-based differences in biological mechanisms, but also to identify research objectives and expected outcomes that may not be achieved or may yield erroneous or incomplete insights if sex and sex-based differences are not taken into account (Tannenbaum *et al.* 2019). Researchers should ensure that sex is an integral component of the research rationale, experimental design, methods, analysis, and knowledge translation (Duchesne *et al.* 2017), and, where not relevant, it can be excluded upon justification (Tannenbaum *et al.* 2019). Ruling out sex without testing its influence in research design can produce wrong results, results that do not apply to male, female, and hermaphrodite organisms.

486 **Figure 1.** Sex analysis in marine biology research by subfields and levels of biological organization
 487 (examples in WebTable 4). In parenthesis (a/b): (a) total number of studies, and (b) percentage of
 488 studies that found sex-based differences within the group of studies.

489

490 **Figure 2. Studies applying sex analysis within marine taxon by level of biological organization**
 491 **and subfield.** In parenthesis (a/b): (a) total number of studies by taxa, and (b) percentage of studies
 492 that found sex-based differences within each taxa. Details are reported in WebTable 5.

493

498 **Table 1.** Guidelines for the integration of sex analysis in field research, laboratory or field
499 experiments, mathematical modelling, and meta-analysis. Examples of applications in WebTable 6.

Research methods

(a) Data collection in field research

- Design appropriate sampling strategies and techniques to consider sex of targeted organisms
 - Report and archive data on sex of sampled organisms
 - Explore new non-invasive techniques for sexing organisms in the field
 - Combine genetics and genomics and related techniques for sex determination
 - Combine multiple techniques to detect sex-based population dynamics and patterns
 - Question how sex can affect the process of data collection
 - Question whether sampling may result in skewed sex-ratios
 - Analyze the survey data protocols and sampling techniques to detect potential sex bias
-

(b) Laboratory and field experiments

- Include organisms of each sex
 - Proceed in sexing organisms included in the experiment
 - Consider sex based differences in the baseline conditions
 - Consider the influence of sex-based intraspecific variations on the response variables
 - Consider confounding effects or failures because of sex differences
-

(c) Mathematical modelling

- Input data disaggregated by sex (see previous sections)
 - Include sex as an explanatory variable
 - Check any significant differences in the response variables by sex
 - Question whether the selected modelling approach or statistical method consider sex
 - Question whether the model or statistical analysis can include sex-based factors
-

(c) Meta-analysis

- Consider sex when formulating the research question
 - Question why sex was not included in the set of studies explored
 - Run sex-based sensitivity analysis on original studies
 - Explore sex-based variance of the results
 - Analyze the role of sex in the set of original studies
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